

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**
[ISSN: 0975-4725; CODEN(USA): IJPS00]
Journal Homepage: <https://www.ijpsjournal.com>

Review Article

A Review Article On Cyclodextrin As A Type Of Nanosponges

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ARTICLE INFO

Published: 20 Oct 2024

Keywords:

Nanosponges, poor solubility, cyclodextrin, crosslinked polymers, multipurpose structure.

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.13958113

ABSTRACT

This paper looks at cyclodextrin-based nanosponges, which are tiny, sponge-like structures made from solid polymers that are linked together. Cyclodextrins, which come from starch, are ring-shaped molecules made of glucose. They have a unique design with a water-loving outside and a water-repelling inside, allowing them to trap and stabilize hydrophobic substances, making those substances easier to dissolve and use. Because of their adaptable nature and large surface area, these nanosponges have mainly been used in the pharmaceutical and biomedical fields for the past 20 years, and they are safe for human use. This paper reviews the progress made with these nanosponges and also looks at their potential for other important uses, like cleaning up contaminated water and soil and in chemical processes.

INTRODUCTION

Cyclodextrins (CDs) are interesting molecules made up of linked glucose units. There are three main types: α -, β -, and γ -cyclodextrin, which contain 6, 7, and 8 glucose units, respectively. They have a unique shape, like a truncated cone or torus, with a water-repelling (hydrophobic) cavity in the center and a water-attracting (hydrophilic) outer surface thanks to hydroxyl groups ($-\text{OH}$). This structure allows cyclodextrins to interact with a variety of compounds, making them soluble in water. They can form special complexes with substances like surfactants, drugs, organic pollutants, dyes, and metal ions through interactions like hydrophobic effects and hydrogen

bonding. Because of this versatility, cyclodextrins are useful in many areas, including pharmaceuticals, food technology, textiles, wastewater treatment, detergents, and paper production. The hydroxyl groups on cyclodextrins are very reactive, which means they can participate in chemical reactions. This allows them to be combined with other materials or linked to different organic or inorganic substances, broadening their potential uses.

Characteristic feature of cyclodextrin:

- **Cyclic Structure:**

Cyclodextrins are made up of linked glucose units that form a ring shape. The most common types—

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Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

α -, β -, and γ -cyclodextrins—contain 6, 7, and 8 glucose units, respectively.

- **Hydrophobic Cavity:**

They have a water-repelling inner cavity, which allows them to trap hydrophobic (water-hating) molecules.

- **Hydrophilic Exterior:**

The outer surface of cyclodextrins is water-attracting because of the hydroxyl (–OH) groups. This makes them soluble in water.

Cyclodextrins can form special complexes with various compounds, which helps improve the solubility and stability of those substances.

- **Chemical Reactivity:**

Their hydroxyl groups are reactive, allowing cyclodextrins to undergo chemical modifications and reactions, such as being linked together.

- **Cross-Linking Capability:**

They can be cross-linked with other materials to create gels or nanoparticles, which expands their range of applications.

- **Biocompatibility:**

Cyclodextrins are generally safe and non-toxic, making them suitable for use in pharmaceuticals and biomedical applications.

- **Stability:**

They are stable under different environmental conditions, which helps them effectively encapsulate other compounds.

- **Thermal Stability:**

Cyclodextrins can withstand heat well, making them useful in processes that involve high temperatures.

- **Diverse Applications:**

Thanks to these features, cyclodextrins are used in various fields, including pharmaceuticals, food technology, cosmetics, textiles, and environmental cleanup.

Cyclodextrin based nanosponges for drug delivery:

Cyclodextrin-based nanosponges are innovative systems designed to deliver drugs more effectively. They take advantage of the unique properties of cyclodextrins to enhance how well medications dissolve, remain stable, and are absorbed in the body. These nanosponges are made by linking cyclodextrins with substances like epichlorohydrin, forming a three-dimensional structure with lots of tiny pores. This design provides a large surface area, allowing them to hold more drugs. The inner cavity of cyclodextrins can capture poorly soluble drugs through a process called inclusion complexation, which helps those drugs work better. Moreover, cyclodextrin nanosponges allow for controlled release of the medication over time, meaning the drug is released steadily rather than all at once. This can improve the effectiveness of the treatment and reduce the side effects that often come with rapid drug release

Cyclodextrin based nanosponges for drug delivery

Types of Cyclodextrins

Cyclodextrins are categorized by the number of glucose units they contain. The most common types are:

1. Alpha-Cyclodextrin (α -CD):

- Made up of six glucose units.
- Has a small cavity, making it ideal for capturing smaller molecules.

2. Beta-Cyclodextrin (β -CD):

- Consists of seven glucose units.
- The most commonly used type, with a medium-sized cavity that can hold a variety of hydrophobic compounds.

3. Gamma-Cyclodextrin (γ -CD):

- Contains eight glucose units.
- Has a larger cavity, allowing it to encapsulate bigger molecules and other guest compounds

Application of cyclodextrin:

1. Pharmaceuticals:

• **Drug Delivery:**

Enhance the solubility and absorption of poorly soluble drugs, improving their therapeutic effects.

• **Controlled Release:**

Enable gradual release of active ingredients, reducing side effects and prolonging effectiveness.

2. Food Industry:

• **Flavor and Aroma Stabilization:**

Encapsulate flavors and aromas to keep them fresh and release them gradually in food products.

• **Nutrient Protection:**

Shield vitamins and delicate nutrients from degradation during processing and storage.

3. Cosmetics and Personal Care:

• **Active Ingredient Delivery:**

Encapsulate active ingredients to enhance their stability and effectiveness in creams and lotions.

• **Fragrance Encapsulation:**

Stabilize fragrances, prolonging their scent in cosmetic products.

4. Environmental Applications:

• **Pollutant Removal:**

Capture and isolate environmental pollutants, aiding in air and water purification.

• **Soil Remediation:**

Help extract or immobilize contaminants in soil.

5. Analytical Chemistry:

• **Separation Techniques:**

Used in chromatography to separate compounds, including enantiomers.

• **Sensors:**

Incorporated into sensors for detecting specific substances.

6. Biomedical Research:

• **Gene Delivery:**

Assist in delivering genetic material and therapeutic agents to cells.

• **Imaging Agents:**

Improve the delivery and effectiveness of agents used in medical imaging.

7. Agriculture:

• **Pesticide Formulations:**

Enhance the solubility and stability of pesticides, increasing their effectiveness while minimizing environmental impact

CONCLUSIONS:

There are various methods for encapsulation, which involve covering a small particle of an active ingredient with an outer layer. Encapsulation can also happen at the molecular level. One way to do this is by using a group of carbohydrates called cyclodextrins (CDs). These molecules can trap other substances, either fully or partially, inside their hollow structure. This ability to form inclusion complexes could lead to new solutions for many future formulations.

REFERENCE:

1. SHANKER SWAMINATHAN P.R.VAVIA Formulation of beta cyclodextrin based nanosponges of itraconazole
2. <http://hdl.handle.net/2318/1660043> Evolution of Cyclodextrin Nanosponges

3. C. U. Shah College of Pharmacy S.N.D.T. Women's University, Santacruz Mumbai-400049, India Cyclodextrin based nanosponges for pharmaceutical use
4. review Article in Asian Pacific Journal of Tropical Disease September 2014 Nanosponges: A potential nanocarrier for novel drug delivery-a
5. Samskruthi College of Pharmacy, Ghatkesar, Ranga Reddy-Dist-501301, Telangana, India NANOSPONGES-NOVEL EMERGING DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEM: A REVIEW
6. Cellular Nanosponges for Biological Neutralization Shuyan Wang, Dan Wang, Yaou Duan, Zhidong Zhou, Weiwei Gao,* and Liangfang Zhang*
7. Innovative Functionalized Paper Solutions. Nordpuip Pap. Res. 1. 34, 395-416 doi:10.1515/upprj-2019-0036
8. DCP. Trotta, F, Kodiwah, V., Devesari, N., Singh, C. Suresh, S, (2016) Potential of Erlotinib Cyclodextrin Nancsponge Complex to Enhance
9. surfactant Inclusion Complexes: An Integrated View of Their Thermodynarnic Structural Properties. Adu Colid Interf Sex 2021.102375 289, 102175 do 10.1016/Fenyvvn, F. Park, K., Gris, K., Vanga, F. Kenyeres, 1, Zaray, G, et al. (2000)
10. Ferro, M. Castiglione F (2017). Dynamnica a and lateractions of thuprofen in Cyckodextrin Nannsponges by Solid-State NMR Spectroscopy. Beiktrin Org Gum 15, 183-194 doe 10. 3762/bjoc.13.21
11. igueiras, A., Sarragoça, J. M. G, Carvalho, R. a. Pais. A. A. CC, and Venga, FJ (2007). Inalio of Oumpraanle with Methylated Derivative of B
12. Animatic Compounds by Hydrogals of Chitosen Blended with 5-cyclodextrin PVA- Functionsned Pectin. RSC Adv. 14809-14622 do: 10.10991 CHRA02332H

HOW TO CITE: Komal Chavan, Kavita Kulkarni, Ashish Faltankar , A Review Article On Cyclodextrin As A Type Of Nanosponges, *Int. J. of Pharm. Sci.*, 2024, Vol 2, Issue 10, 1174-1177. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13958113>